

Primed for programming: facets of a practical epistemology of tech

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Abstract

How best to nurture knowledge and expertise in applied computing, a.k.a. ‘tech’, is a subject of vital contemporary concern. Here the tech knowledge space is considered in relation to how certain cognitive processes might operate on and within it, the aim being to arrive at a perspective capable of shedding light on how technologists might be assisted as they go about locating, assimilating and utilizing information. Ideas from cognitive science and elsewhere provide raw materials from which to assemble a proto-theoretical framework which may contain useful pointers for educators, learning technologists and providers of information products and services.

Keywords:

cognitive psychology, creativity, expertise, knowledge, problem solving, programming, software development, technology, tech information

Introduction

A software developer or computer programmer is perhaps the quintessential knowledge worker. Programmers’ working lives revolve around information and data. Software applications and systems are the engines and factories of information production, processing, distribution, and assimilation into knowledge, and their creation is a fundamentally cognitive activity. A trope familiar to the programming community is that of the programmer as a mechanism for converting coffee and pizza into lines of code, and the operating core of that stereotype-laden conception is knowledge: of one or more programming languages, of data formats, of computing theory and concepts, of algorithms, of protocols and standards. Given the centrality of applied computing, or ‘tech’, to the functioning of modern societies, there is obvious potential value in reflecting on the nature of tech knowledge, and on how its absorption, transmission and utilization might best be fostered and supported. In this article I attempt to do just that, by examining some of the topics that are surely key components in any practical epistemology of tech.

I begin by reviewing the present state of tech information, before moving on to consider how information is located, and what happens to it once located. I speculate on aspects of its assimilation into knowledge, and think about programming as an activity in which knowledge is applied to the solution of problems. My treatment of these topics, each of which is of course dauntingly enormous

in its own right, is necessarily highly selective and partial, but by focusing on particular aspects it may become possible to view some of the elements with greater clarity. That, at least, is my motivating hope.

The state of tech information

The technology information space is large and heterogeneous, reflecting the tech domain itself. The component strands of that domain are drawn from a variety of disciplines besides computer science, including mathematics, linguistics, psychology, cognitive science, neuroscience, electronic engineering, and business studies. It encompasses the burgeoning fields of artificial intelligence and data science, which are connected via the shared sub-disciplines of machine learning and computer vision, amongst others. All these fields have theoretical and more practical aspects, as does the core discipline of programming. Algorithmic principles are realized and realizable via dozens of programming languages, each with their own traits and talents, and each often associated with multiple functionally specialized frameworks and libraries. Shaping the space further are numerous cross-cutting fields, such as cybersecurity, web development, and the internet of things. Distinct themes in tech may be individuated according to a variety of criteria, including application area, methodological focus, hierarchical position in a technology stack, or relevance to a particular role within an organization.

As well as being complex and multi-dimensional, the tech space is continuously growing and evolving. Other fields of knowledge are expanding rapidly too, of course, but the growth of tech has a distinctive feature. This is the fact, as I see it, that its expansion increasingly outpaces the growth of high-quality information about it. In part this is because technologists have a well-known aversion to documenting their work – which agile principles threaten to turn into a virtue¹ – and partly it is because much of the information that *is* produced tends to be fragmentary, transient, and collectively heterogeneous.² Limited lifetime web pages on vendor sites; files of software release notes unknown to all except especially dedicated users of the relevant applications; blog posts of extremely variable quality scattered across a multitude of sites; the odd arXiv preprint, if you happen to be looking; occasional volumes of conference proceedings, their contents ranging from broad brush summaries to articles so detailed that the wood is scarcely visible amongst the trees; superficial sales pitches masquerading as white papers – such is the state of the information space surrounding new and emerging tech.

Arguably it was not always thus: software applications used to come boxed and accompanied by a hefty manual or two; *Byte* magazine and its ilk enjoyed significant success prior to the eclipse of print by the web, and served as important aggregators and disseminators of information that made sense of developments across large tracts of the tech landscape. Now, it might be argued that the ever-growing state of tech demonstrates that even if there is an information shortfall of some kind, it doesn't much matter. I am sceptical of that, however; it seems only too likely that there is a substantial epistemic price to be paid for the ephemerality and disconnectedness of so much tech information. It can be especially hard to compare technology alternatives, hampering decision-making. Lack of awareness of the latest developments doubtless results in missed opportunities and unnecessary

¹ <https://agilemanifesto.org>

² I exclude from this negative characterization, of course, the efforts of specialist tech book publishers like my employer, and more importantly the efforts of their authors, to bring order to the information chaos.

duplications of effort; to learn and master particular technologies is made more burdensome, imposing an inertial barrier that probably limits uptake; time is wasted on out-of-date materials.

The contrast between information about new and emerging tech and that relating to developments in science is stark. In science we find a relatively orderly array of subject-specific primary research and review journals, as well as a number of prestigious broad-spectrum journals like *Nature* and *Science*. All contain peer-validated articles that are consistently structured, granularly indexed, and readily searchable by a variety of services. Articles cite the work they draw on, so that the intellectual antecedents and connections of a proposal or finding are exposed, and narrative norms ensure that context in relation to similar work is readily apparent.³ We are not comparing like with like, it is true. Science puts theoretically inspired experimental questions to nature, and gauges the fit with theory of the answers that nature returns. The congruence, or not, of theoretical predictions with reality determines the next set of questions to be asked. This methodology has shown itself to be remarkably capable in enabling science to iteratively home in on theoretical perspectives of ever-greater reach, accuracy and effectiveness. Tech, on the other hand, is a more synthetic and commercially motivated enterprise, where ideas are combined to create artefacts intended to meet diverse, open-ended and evolving human and organizational needs. It is not so much a case of homing in as branching out. And while the tech information space includes coverage of fundamental conceptual developments, perhaps the greater part of it is taken up with material relating to their application.

In light of the informational shortcomings just described, it is interesting to note what can perhaps be seen as internally driven adaptive responses of the tech world to its information needs. Resources like StackOverflow play a major part in providing developers with real-time answers to the tech implementation questions that daily arise in their work. Even with the availability of such tools, however, mastery of any major branch of tech is a significant accomplishment. Solving real-world tech problems generally demands familiarity with an extensive set of concepts and techniques. Attaining that familiarity is almost invariably cognitively effortful, even if the degree of difficulty depends on the abilities of the individual concerned. Knowledge barriers are lowered when relevant information is available, but efficient mechanisms are required to make that information discoverable. Technologists of differing abilities must be able to find the information most relevant to their specific needs, whatever those happen to be. Typically the goal is to grow one's knowledge or accomplish some specific practical task, although that disjunction is an artificial one, in that often the best way to grow one's knowledge in tech is *by* attempting to accomplish a practical task. That is something I shall return to. First, however, I want to provide a quick gloss on search, since that will put us in a suitable frame of mind for entering the epistemic thickets that follow.

Search and discovery: semi-psychological processes

The term *search and discovery* (S&D) is used in relation on the one hand to the activities of seeking and finding computerized information, and on the other to the tools that support those activities. The bracketing together of search and discovery within a single term makes considerable sense, since they overlap extensively as regards both activities and tools. Where a distinction has to be drawn, it is common to speak of search as pertaining to the rapid identification and location of content about a specific topic, where there is a presumption that such content exists or might exist. Discovery is seen

³ This reading of the scholarly publishing sphere is perhaps a little idealized, but not I think excessively so.

as a more exploratory and open-ended activity. It can involve finding out what information exists, in general or about a specific subject, within a collection or resource, and learning about its composition and extent. Discovery may also embrace the encountering or locating of particular content items relevant to specific goals and interests, such an outcome being similar to that of successful search activity.⁴

Since the processes of S&D involve the interaction of humans with machines, they inevitably have a significant psychological dimension. This can be seen when we consider the following diagram of S&D processes:

The diagram oversimplifies things, no doubt, but it does direct our attention towards several important features of S&D processes:

- They are typically cyclical, involving loops of interaction between mind and machine, between user and content resource
- The user in an S&D process is a cognitive agent who engages with an information system by formulating search queries or by interacting with a user interface
- There are few steps in the S&D process that are not significantly shaped by the psychological nature of the user. Information in content resides in epistemic packages of various kinds – diagrams, verbal explanations, videos, etc. – and these must be perceived, identified as being potentially relevant to the user’s needs, and interpreted so that meaning can be assessed and extracted. These are all heavily cognitive processes. Then comes assimilation, in which the semantic payload of an epistemic package is incorporated into the user’s existing stock of knowledge. (Although perhaps we should think of interpretation and assimilation as being interwoven, rather than seeing them as neatly discrete, sequential operations.)

⁴ The notion of success applies with more force to search than to discovery, however, since the goals of search are typically more clear-cut. One searches in the hope of finding, whereas one explores more in the hope of learning, and it is hard to engage with an information resource but learn nothing.

Often spoken of in the same breath as search(ing), and contrasted with it, are browsing and navigating, terms which these days require no explanation. Searching is generally thought to be more cognitively demanding than browsing. Aula (2005), citing Cothey, writes:

Considered in cognitive terms, search is a more analytical and demanding method for locating information than browsing, as it involves several phases, such as planning and executing queries, evaluating the results, and refining the queries, whereas browsing only requires the user to recognize promising-looking results. (p.14)

One other term sometimes used in the same broad conceptual space, which perhaps does require elucidation, is 'sensemaking'. This has been described as 'an iterative process of formulating a conceptual representation of a large volume of information', involving information retrieval through searching and browsing, sometimes in combination with analysis and synthesis of results (Hearst 2009, p.80). Sensemaking is an active process, in other words, in which the user harnesses and switches adaptively and pragmatically between a variety of distinct techniques.

I take S&D activities to subsume all these different processes. The cognitive tasks of information interpretation and assimilation are, presumably, shaped in part by the information culture to which the user has been exposed. Good information product design depends on achieving congruence with respect to a particular information culture – an informational habitus, if you will – as well as with more culturally independent aspects of human psychology. But the most important factor affecting how information is processed is the state of the user's prior knowledge.

Representing knowledge

Of course, knowledge has been a philosophically problematic concept for some millennia, and I shall not presume here to claim an ability to cut through the Gordian Knot. Let's simply(!) say for now that knowledge is about the possession (as it were) of complex sets of psychological dispositions of various kinds, which can often be thought of as being based on mental representations of different sorts succeeding each other in various ways under various conditions, such that very broadly our thoughts align with facts about, and events in, the world. When this alignment exists, we gain the ability to understand and predict events, and engage as effective agents in the world; we may think of ourselves as being knowledgeable, because we possess knowledge.⁵ Not to be overlooked, however, is the importance of tacit skills, and likewise the complex interplay of belief and practice that underpins understanding and effective action.⁶ A virtue of the dispositional stance is that it appears capable of accommodating the dimension of practice, and in this it hints at the possibility of a unified account of knowledge, understanding, embodiment, and agency.

It can be helpful to think of knowledge in terms of mental models (Craik 1943; Johnson-Laird 1983). These are cognitive widgets we use to explain how things work, capturing causal and other relations as well as intuitions about how we stand in relation to things, and how we may exert our agency. There may be value too in conceiving, in somewhat metaphorical vein, of mental models as involving schemata operating on a range of representational structures such as knowledge graphs. These are data structures composed of nodes representing concepts and entities, connected by edges standing for particular kinds of relation (Kejriwal, Knoblock and Szekely 2021). Being knowledgeable

⁵ Only by an effort of will have I resisted here the inclination to put quotation marks around both 'possess' and 'knowledge', for I am doubtful whether knowledge, as we conventionally employ the term, has any straightforwardly correspondent structural referent(s) inside our heads. (Likewise for beliefs).

⁶ Regarding the importance of tacit skills for understanding, see de Regt (2009).

would then mean having at one's disposal a battery of effective mental models, or schemata capable of acting on a sizable and highly interconnected personal knowledge graph. Knowledge of tech, a field in which referential specificity tends to be rather greater than in many other fields, is probably quite amenable to this way of thinking.

We can also think of approximating textual information and other content in graph terms, with nodes standing for subjects, objects, topics and concepts, and those nodes connected by relational edges, e.g. verbs, and commonly decorated with property descriptors. For an individual to grow their own knowledge graph by interacting with a graph of content would mean replicating some of the nodes and edges of the content graph within their own personal knowledge graph. For this learning process to be possible, the graphs must have some nodes in common to start with, presumably. Content contains new information for the user when the content graph contains unshared nodes connected to some of the nodes the graphs share.

To ingest and assimilate new information from content requires alignment of the content graph with the user's knowledge graph. During alignment, the nodes shared by the two graphs are identified and brought into registration. Where the same terms are used for semantically equivalent nodes this is generally straightforward, although of course some terms have synonyms, and in different languages the same concepts, entities etc. are typically referred to using different words. In the former case (synonyms) we expect alignment to occur fractionally slower than usual, while in the latter case we know by introspection, from experience of translating a foreign language, that alignment can be slowed considerably. If the user's knowledge graph and the content graph have *no* nodes in common, then alignment is impossible, and the user finds the content incomprehensible. Relatable and readily digested content, on the other hand, includes multiple shared nodes, which act as touchpoints for comprehension.

Problems and solutions

In tech, as already alluded to, knowledge commonly has a practical character: users learn in order to understand, but then typically they seek to apply their understanding in the construction of software systems. These systems represent solutions to practical problems, expressing in mechanistic terms how to accomplish particular information processing tasks.

A problem solution can be seen as a particular configuration or assembly of ideas, with a highly creative solution being one that combines elegance and effectiveness with improbability. Following our earlier line of thought, maybe one way of thinking about the ideas that come together in a problem solution is as particular subsets of nodes and connections in a knowledge graph, i.e. as sub-graphs. Where several distinct solutions to a problem exist, we would then say that there are multiple sub-graphs that satisfy the constraints posed by the problem. Greater knowledge, qua a more extensive and more richly connected knowledge graph, facilitates problem solving because it increases the likelihood that the knowing subject potentially has access to a problem-solving complex of ideas. But if operations on graphs depend on our schemata, then even if a graph 'contained the answer' in principle, that answer might not be found if schemata capable of forming an effective mental model were not available.

To turn a set of ideas into a solution requires, we are saying, the ability to manipulate the ideas – explore their degrees of freedom – to find an overall configuration that is indeed a solution to the problem. In the generate-and-test, or evolutionary, perspective on problem solving (Campbell 1960),

the idea is that the search for a solution involves the generation and evaluation of multiple solution candidates, with the optimal or fittest solution being the one that best endures the rigours of evaluation.

The generation of a candidate solution depends on the selection, configuration, and combination of solution elements, and these stages are (I'm suggesting) schemata-driven operations. As in the case of interpretation and assimilation touched on earlier, it is probably unwise to think of them as purely sequential stages, however; it seems likely that they are commingled at least to some degree. Perhaps experience and the tacit knowledge it confers sometimes make their presence felt as biases in the propensity to select certain elements in combination, say, or to configure them in particular ways. This will reduce the likelihood of some element complexes being generated, even before any more explicit evaluation stage can occur. Some of these biases from experience may actually hinder the generation of complexes that represent potentially good solutions, and perhaps that is part of the explanation for the rarity of creative solutions. (And perhaps what is sometimes referred to as genius is the ability to create rare but effective solutions by sidestepping, or not being susceptible to, conventional biases.)⁷

Primed for programming

At this point let's turn away from such comparative abstractions and think about the nature of programming. A computer program is made up of lines of code, which typically consist of statements specifying operations to be performed on named entities called variables. A variable can be thought of as a container for data of a particular type. Programming languages recognize a range of different data types, including strings of text characters, integers and real numbers, and various groupings of such entities, such as arrays and lists. Thinking about GUI (graphical user interface) applications, much of the work of the programmer consists in writing code that will be triggered by interface events. Those events will occur when users of the application interact with it, as it appears on their screens, and they include such things as button clicks, entry of text into particular interface objects, selections being made from drop-down lists, etc.

As an example, suppose that a hypothetical programmer – let's call him Algy – is tasked with writing an application that must connect to a database, obtain various pieces of textual and numerical data from it, combine them, and then display the result. Algy needs to know many things, besides the basic facts about such entities as databases and data. He needs to know how, in whatever language he is using, to connect to a database of a certain kind, how to write suitable queries, how to get the database to execute the queries, how to extract any query results from the results sets returned by the database, how to combine and format the information from the various results sets, and how to display the end result in his application. For each operation Algy wants to perform, there are specific commands and keywords he needs to know, and he needs to be able to construct statements that are valid in themselves and which connect together as a whole so as to conform to the syntax of the language. And he will quite possibly already have had to conceive the architecture of, and then build,

⁷ I am conscious that my thoughts about these topics are, in all likelihood, being steered to some extent by the experience of having once taken a stimulating course entitled 'Computers and Creativity' with Prof. Margaret Boden at Sussex University, as part of the Knowledge-Based Systems masters programme. Reading for the course included MB's own *The Creative Mind: Myths and Mechanisms* and D.N. Perkins' *The Mind's Best Work*, and any debts to ideas in those two works (or indeed in others which do not presently come to mind) are freely acknowledged.

an overall application into which the database connection/data extraction code can slot. In relation to all of these tasks he will have had to draw on considerable amounts of knowledge.

What, cognitively, might be involved in what Algy is seeking to accomplish? At the very outset there probably comes a conceptualization and design stage, based perhaps on a written project brief – or maybe a sketch on the back of an envelope – from a product manager or some other stakeholder. Algy has to interpret the brief and turn it into an idea for an application. If the objective is a GUI application, that is presumably in part a visualization problem (what should the running application look like?), but one where what must be envisaged is not a static image but a composite object that has latent functional potentialities, akin in some ways to a machine. (Developers sometimes speak of the ‘moving parts’ of a software system.) Probably there will be decisions to be made about how best to combine the information extracted by the different database queries, and how to display it. Perhaps the text is stored in the database in a different format from that which can be displayed, in which case Algy needs to find a way for his application to transform the text from one format to the other. That might involve using a transformation-specific language distinct from the language he's using to write his application, or that used to query the database. Maybe his application will have to execute another, external, application or script (written in yet another language?) to carry out the transformation. Potential complexities abound.

One of the more fundamental questions relating to what Algy is doing, given all the languages potentially involved, is what it is to ‘know’ a programming language. The parallel with knowing a natural language appears close, for there is a vocabulary and a syntax, and statements made using the terms of the language may be meaningful or not. As with a natural language, some terms refer to objects and entities of various kinds, while others serve to establish larger causal/semantic structures (e.g. in relation to flow control). To know a language one needs to know what the key terms are, have an intuitive sense of the syntactic categories to which they belong, and grasp the rules for combining them to create meaningful statements. One way to think about the specific functions or roles of terms within a programming language is as valences or affinities for other terms; knowing about the role of some specific term serves to constrain the set of terms it can legitimately succeed, and that can legitimately succeed it. (This can be thought of as a potential example of knowledge as disposition, as trailed previously.)

It is interesting to compare how a programmer attains familiarity with the key terms in a programming language and how natural languages are learnt, as regards how term roles are assimilated. Michael Hoey's theory of lexical priming posits that we develop a sense of how words function in a natural language – what their roles are – not by explicitly learning the rules of grammar, but rather by being exposed over time to large numbers of word instances in their natural contexts. It is this that drives the automatic development of the appropriate associations between terms, as the brain acquires a sense of word association probabilities (Hoey 2005). Grammar, for Hoey, is thus effectively an emergent phenomenon. It does not seem unreasonable to suppose that lexical priming is a significant contributor to the development of fluency in a programming language, even if we might balk at the idea that priming is the fundamental driver of programming language learning in the way that Hoey contends it is for natural language acquisition. In other words, maybe learning a programming language is something of a hybrid case where priming is concerned, where the understanding that comes from explicit learning of syntax is reinforced by priming effects that come from exposure over time to quantities of code.

There are also several notable quantitative differences between natural languages and programming languages, from which might follow important qualitative differences. The first concerns the size of the vocabularies involved: most programming languages consist of several dozen or so keywords, whereas natural language vocabularies are some hundreds of times larger (at the individual speaker level). The second contrast relates to syntactic complexity. Now natural language grammars – viewed as codifications of emergent syntax, to buy into lexical priming – are no less complex than the syntax of a typical programming language. (*Au contraire*, surely.) So it seems reasonable to suppose that natural language assertions of some given length are liable to be more varied than assertions of the same length in any programming language. What this could mean – and this is something of a leap, I acknowledge – is that more ‘cognitive capacity’ is available in principle to the programmer for conceiving structures over *large scales* in a programming language than is available to the user of a natural language.⁸ Thus, with exposure to sufficient volumes of code, a programmer might find it possible to conceive of code running to thousands of lines. Indeed, isn’t this what we already know to be the case: that experienced programmers do have such a facility? Moreover, the capability difference between the least able and the most able programmers is marked, as regards speed of coding and time spent debugging.⁹ Should we say this is down to priming effects, or imaginative capability? Most probably it is a combination of the two, but – so my intuitions incline me to believe – weighted towards the latter.

Software-building as explanation

Talk of imagination brings me to another, perhaps rather unexpected, idea: that the artefacts the programmer produces, i.e. tech solutions, stand comparison with the explanations we routinely give of events and phenomena in the world. Explanation is a well-developed branch of philosophy of science (see e.g. Ruben 1993; Psillos 2002), but as might be expected it is a topic that interests psychologists too. One explanatory phenomenon which has received considerable attention is the so-called self-explanation effect, whereby explaining a problem or situation to oneself or another person often enables one to reach an understanding that is otherwise elusive (Chi et al. 1994; Ainsworth & Loizou 2003; see also Lombrozo 2016). My rough take on the phenomenon is that it stems from the fact that when we explain, we are compelled to straighten out our thoughts, as it were, by identifying salient relationships between elements identified as relevant to the situation at hand. We must relate our thoughts to the properties of those elements, make explicit the operative patterns of causality, be clear about issues of temporal sequence, and so on. Often this amounts to an imaginative process in which sets of ideas are, perhaps partly sub-consciously, explored, manipulated and configured. Successfully imagining how something happens or why it is the case means ordering our thoughts in such a way that the dispositions we have around the individual conceptual components that figure as

⁸ This glosses over some important differences between programming languages, which potentially impact on the extent to which, and the respects in which, they impose cognitive loads of various kinds on their users. XSLT and Prolog spring to mind as ‘troublesome’ languages, and I suspect their difficulty stems from the way in which lines of code written in these languages often fail to reflect the complexities of internal processing that determine the results of code execution. In other words, it can be hard for the programmer to mentally simulate the results of running the code they write. Languages like this generally fail to achieve widespread or enduring adoption.

⁹ See e.g. Weinberg (1971), p.135, where productivity differences of 30:1 are granted as plausible, albeit in relation to specific aspects of the programming role. (It is suggested that because individual programmers excel in different aspects of their roles, but few excel in all, overall differences for the role viewed in toto will be smaller.) Differences of these sorts of magnitude have been disputed, however, e.g. by Nichols (2019).

elements of the focus of imagination (some of which dispositions we sometimes refer to as beliefs) are mutually supporting.

Prior to the act of explaining, we entertain a set of ideas and beliefs, but they are somewhat disconnected and disorganized; the relations between different elements are not fully worked out; we have not configured them such that their dispositions sum constructively. Sometimes, in developing an explanation we might enlarge or modify the set of elements to be integrated. An explanation is a serialized version of the prior set of conceptual elements, where the elements form a dispositionally coherent whole in which term affinities (and perhaps other, higher order, constraints) are honoured, and where the whole is amenable to verbal expression. When we achieve a concatenation of ideas where one thought leads naturally to the next, something seems to us to be intelligible, and we experience the feeling of understanding. When such an explanation is transmitted and received by another, its structure is such as to engender an aptly configured set of ideas in that other's mind, and the expression is thus explanatory for the recipient.

A tech solution is, I'd like to claim, rather like an explanation, in that as with the pre-explanatory state described above, the starting point (or at least one of the starting points) is a set or complex of inter-related ideas. In the case of application building, these ideas don't get linearized into a temporal sequence, but rather they get worked out and transformed into a machine-like causal structure, in an active process of manipulation, exploration and configuration that has to satisfy multiple constraints (e.g. syntactic, functional, aesthetic). And at the code block level, there *is* a quasi-linguistic linearization of ideas.¹⁰ The important point is that almost never do the initial ideas get worked out or configured fully unless, or until, an attempt is made to build the application. This, I suspect, is generally for reasons of cognitive burden: the ideas are too numerous or complex for the mind to readily manipulate them in memory. Hence, to see whether a software idea is viable, or to work out how best to implement an idea, as often as not there's no substitute for rolling up one's sleeves and getting stuck into some practical software development.

Expertise in tech

Levels of expertise in tech, as in any field of human endeavour, vary widely. It is intuitively appealing to suppose that expertise is a function of two components: experience and innate ability. An obvious first thought here is that experience is largely dependent simply on 'flying hours', i.e. the amount of time an individual has spent engaged in some activity, such as coding. How it is measured may be complicated, however, by issues of granularity and relevance. If what we are interested in is overall programming experience, then the time spent using each of a number of different programming languages would be relevant, but what should we take to be indicative of experience with something more nebulous like data-handling? That will depend on how we see activities as relating to each other, and on perceived groupings and similarities. Nor can experience just be about time. When wearing a recruitment hat, say, we might be inclined to treat some experiences as being more valuable, more likely to have resulted in learning and the acquisition of useful skills and knowledge, than others, even if there were no difference in terms of 'time spent'.

Maybe one can think of innate ability as a multiplier or scaling factor, the value of which determines how much useful expertise results from a given quantum of experience. But in treating it

¹⁰ Although often rules of code layout implicate, to a greater or lesser extent, a second spatial dimension, making coding arguably more akin to writing poetry than prose.

as a single value like this, we should remember that the value represents multiple factors, reflecting the many and varied cognitive dimensions by which individuals differ and demonstrate talent. Focusing on software developers, let's accept a crude binary distinction between novice or growing developers and expert developers. The difference between these two categories could be characterized operationally, in relation to several related capabilities. First, an expert developer is adept at turning a description of end user needs into an idea for a solution, and if necessary resolving that idea into a workable design which could then be implemented. Another skill of the expert is almost the complement of this: the ability to see a working solution, or alternatively a surface description of a software system and its behaviour, and on the basis of that postulate an underlying architecture. If needs be they could flesh out this architecture with detailed tech choices and configurations so as to functionally replicate the original solution.

Being able to move among and translate between surface descriptions, detailed designs and working implementations in this way requires mental models that accurately represent the characteristics of different technologies, and the sort of richly populated mental knowledge graph discussed earlier. It may also draw on a well-developed capability for visualization. Figuratively we may in addition say it is a matter of having the right ontologies, into which nodes of the mental knowledge graph are appropriately connected, and the ability to navigate around detailed mental taxonomies. Having these capabilities means that the expert can move with ease among different levels of abstraction, and often (depending on their experience) between functionally equivalent nodes within different alternative tech ecosystems. Perhaps therefore it is not so much that there is one key cognitive ingredient that distinguishes the talented developer from the mediocre, but rather that the former – besides possibly having an extensive back-catalogue of programming hits to draw on – has an unusual *combination* of attributes. To those listed above, we should probably add a particular facility for employing multiple styles of mental representation, and for switching between different styles at will, appropriately, and according to the task at hand.¹¹

Assisting the technologist

The goal of turning mediocre software developers into talented ones might be an unduly ambitious one for tech information providers to espouse, if that would require, hypothetically, the installation or upgrading of cognitive capacities that may be grounded largely in heredity. But if we could pin down the cognitive foundations of programming expertise we would be in a much better place to tailor online information resources and associated functionality to the needs of particular groups of users in relation to specific software development tasks. Then we might help mediocre programmers become more effective, and talented programmers more effective still.

Perhaps the most fundamental need for novice developers is to acquire robust ontologies and models of the tech knowledge space, so that they know what kinds of entity exist, and what their functional relations are. Without a basic map to guide us it is hard to know where new information should be placed, hindering our ability to turn it into knowledge that can serve as food for the imagination. That means helping novice developers build out their personal knowledge graphs with features like topic maps and exploratory aids of various kinds. The aim should be to make it as easy as possible to move around the tech landscape, so that its contours can be readily discerned. Discrete

¹¹ For insight into some of the academic debates attending the cognitive psychology of programming, see e.g. Détienne (1990), Petre & Blackwell (1999), Good & Howland (2016), and Román-González et al. (2018).

examples of particular points in tech, and long-form projects that illustrate end-to-end approaches to particular problems, would help novices absorb ontologies and mental models, in part through lexical priming-type reinforcement processes. To adopt a faintly Lego-like metaphor, it is by seeing a tech concept in a variety of contexts that its shape, and its various points of flexure and attachment, become familiar. The learner needs to encounter a broad enough sampling of the possible configuration space to develop a sense of a tech idea's potentialities, and appreciate how it fits within the relevant tech subspace.

Search requirements for novice users are perhaps more easily met than those for experts, with relatively straightforward functionality being sufficient to support the 'orienting' style of search that novice users often seem to prefer. This is where a broad initial search, which takes the user to approximately the right part of information space, is followed by a series of navigation operations to reach the desired information (Hearst, p.77). For more advanced users, there may be value in providing additional tools to help manage search results and other data, and facilitate the creation of links with other resources. The aim here would be to help break down the boundaries between different aspects of the user's work and provide a synoptic view of all materials relevant to a task.

More advanced users, having already developed substantial knowledge within one or more tech domains, consequently possess a well-stocked mental workbench of tech concepts from which to build. They may still sometimes need reminders and prompts about how particular things work, however. Then what's required are not fleshed out, context-rich examples but purer, more simplified examples that abstract the tech from context and cut to the syntactic and semantic chase. This will often be the case where the specifics of language statements and commands are concerned. Examples are still helpful here, but they need to be concise and stick to the fundamentals. And organization is critical, of course. Great information architecture can sometimes obviate the need for search functionality altogether (Morville 2005).

Concluding discussion

Having walked through some of the principal facets of a rough epistemology of tech, let's now quickly review the overall picture that emerges. We saw that the tech information space is multiform, and that it tends to lag behind the proliferation of technologies and applications. Nor does it yet greatly facilitate the making of tech comparisons so vital for decision making. Search and discovery are major mechanisms for locating information within the tech information space, but individuals differ markedly as regards their preferred approaches, depending on their experience, learning style and level of knowledge. I advocated taking a dispositional view of knowledge, framed in terms of mental models that involve the operation of cognitive schemata on various kinds of representational entity. The collections of entities on which the schemata operate can, I suggested, perhaps be considered in graph terms.¹²

¹² To undercut what was said previously we maybe ought, sceptically and in a spirit of philosophical naturalism, to ask whether the chief attraction of viewing the representational entities in graph terms is not just that it would be an instrumental convenience for the computational simulation of knowledge-centred processes were we to be able to do so. Does it actually make sense to see a knowledge graph as having the capacity to stand in some sort of parallel relation with cognitive processes in this way? It seems not just conceivable but intrinsic to modern orthodoxy that our cognitive representations do arise out of processes, which at root are neural processes. There is perhaps then a transitive argument to be made that if cognitive representations of the sort that figure in the explanans and explananda of cognitive science can be mapped to graph structures, in the sense that the graph structures capture the relevant relations (and patterns of

Looking at the activity of programming led us to see important roles for processes the neural underpinnings of which are understood in some detail: imagination and visualization. It is now tempting to suggest that those faculties, especially when overlaid with webs of causality,¹³ be seen as particularly important kinds of cognitive schemata. The development of software solutions we saw to be akin to explanation-building in entailing the active reconfiguration of ideas, and individual differences in the ability to carry out such reconfigurations might partly account for observed differences in programming aptitude. This perspective is, I think, a useful one, inasmuch as the emphasis on cognitive factors helps us identify the various points at which technologists of differing aptitudes and levels of knowledge might be assisted in deepening their expertise. There are several notable elephants in the room, however, or rather not in the room.

The first big omission from this discussion is artificial intelligence. The recent advent of generative AI is already exerting significant effects on the tech landscape and beyond.¹⁴ New roles, such as prompt engineering, are coming to the fore, and the job content of established roles in software development is already being reshaped by the availability of AI-based tools such as ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot. It is almost certainly too early to say what the full impact of AI will be over the next few years, although at this stage it feels as though it would be more dangerous to underestimate its likely effects than overestimate them. Certainly we can ask how, given what we have already seen, generative AI will affect what programmers need to know, how they come to know it, and how tech expertise can be fostered. I do not propose to go into these issues now, however, since they warrant a fuller treatment than there is space for here. Nonetheless, it seems critically important to note how different the ‘what’s most likely to come next?’ mechanism of generative AI tools is from common conceptions of how human intelligence works. The impressive abilities of ChatGPT and its kind have been surprising precisely because they appear to have emerged fully formed from the chaos of weights in the underlying neural networks, with never so much as an attempt made to explicitly represent objects, incorporate models of the world, invest rudimentary imaginative capacities, teach categorical distinctions, or indeed include any of the rest of what we supposed would be necessary to instil advanced, seemingly human-level, language capacities in silicon. We are still discovering where the edges lie, but current AI appears to be notably deficient in its ability to respond to the world – still less come to the world – in a value-driven, psychosocially astute way likely to lead to the invention of new sorts of functional kinds and new ways of responding to human needs and wants. In other words, AI might help technologists especially with the ‘how?’ of tech, but for now at least it seems unlikely to be quite as helpful with the ‘what?’.

The second absent pachyderm is sociology: the fact that this discussion has centred on the individual developer as an independent cognitive agent. There the excuse is not recency but simply selectivity: my aim has been to consider tech from a psychological standpoint rather than a sociological one. That is not to deny, however, that software development is typically an intensely social enterprise, and hence one replete with opportunities for information providers to support teams of perhaps somewhat diverse individuals engaged in shared sets of tasks. To address that adequately again warrants a separate project. What is clear, and if anything the rise of AI heightens

causality), and if the cognitive representations map to neural processes, then in principle knowledge graphs could indeed be mapped to neural processes. (Having said that, it feels as though the words ‘in principle’ should be underlined heavily.)

¹³ I go into how causal entailment might figure in mechanistic cognition in the final chapter of Powell (2009) and in the later parts of Powell (2013).

¹⁴ See, for example, Haynes (2023).

the sense of opportunity even as it complicates it, is that we live in a blessed time for the creation of potent information resources. Abilities to index and search, and link and juxtapose – and now summarize, and more – present opportunities to turbocharge technologists of all levels of ability. But making full use of the technological possibilities for transferring knowledge of tech calls for deep insight into the kinds of cognitive agents we are. In relation to that, there is doubtless still much to learn.

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